

Influence of Training and Staffing In the Implementation of Early Childhood Education Programs in Eldoret West Uasin Gishu County

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Abstract

The vision 2030 focuses on Training and research for quality Education which is yet to be accomplished in Educational Institutions. Good Quality Training and staffing ensures effectiveness and efficiencies which plays crucial roles in laying the foundations for improved competences of future citizens, also creates a more skilled workforce capable of contributing and adjusting to technological change. The study was guided by Weber's bureaucratic theory where training and staffing are identified as the main elements in any institutions. The target population included 185 ECDE trained teachers and 236 parents/guardians. The sample size was 55 ECDE teachers and 70 guardians because this represents 30% of each category in all 139 ECD centers in Eldoret west, Uasin Gishu. Random sampling technique was used to select teachers while systematic Random Technique was used to select guardians. Descriptive methods were employed in analyzing qualitative data where frequencies and proportions were used in interpreting. The study was conducted in Eldoret West District, Uasin Gishu County, Kenya. Questionnaires, Interview schedules and observation schedules were used to generate the data required. Descriptive methods were employed in analyzing qualitative data where frequencies and proportions respondent's perception of issues raised in the questionnaires so as to answer the research questions. Findings show that training, staffing, and planning had a positive influence on the implementation of early childhood education in ECDE centers. The recommendations are that ECDC's should acquire knowledge through training of all stakeholders that will enhance effective policy implementations and ensure holistic development of ECD learners.

Key Words; *Influence, training, staffing, implementation, vision 2030, early childhood education*

INTRODUCTION

Researchers, practitioners, and policymakers agree that quality Early Childhood Services and ultimately the outcomes for children and families depend on well-established management programs.

There is clear evidence that high quality ECDE management leads to significantly better attainment in international tests on skills (European commission, 2011).

Training and staffing are essential elements that when put in place will ensure excellent programs are run, skills and knowledge will be acquired which will be relevant in implementing ECDE programs efficiently and effectively (NACECE, 2003).

The quality expertise, training, and staffing will ensure effectiveness and efficiencies where many benefits will be realized ranging from children's good socialization, good health and positive influence on a child's learning and development. It makes a positive impact on a child and gives them a head start towards a bright future (Sutton, 2001).

Teacher Training provisions coupled with quality services create a conducive environment that fosters implementation of ECDE (NACECE, 2003).

MATERIALS AND METHODS

The study was conducted in registered ECDE centers in Eldoret west Uasin Gishu county; random sampling technique was used to select teachers while the systematic random technique was used to select guardians.

The target population for this study was 185 ECDE trained teachers and 236 parents/ guardians.

The sample size was 55 ECDE teachers and 70 guardians because this represents 30% of each category in all 139 registered ECDE centers in Eldoret west Uasin Gishu County.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSIONS

TRAINING IN ECDE

A section of a questionnaire sought to find out if the schools initiated the ECD skills training Program. It was determined that sixteen (29.1%) strongly Agreed (SA), twenty three (41.8%) Agreed (A). This is shown in table 1.

Table 1. Teacher Training

Initiation of ECDE skills training programs

Level response	Frequency	Percentage
Strong agree	16	29.1
Agree (A)	23	41.8
UNDECIDED (u)	4	7.3
Disagree	8	14.5
Strongly disagree	4	7.3
Total	55	100

Source: Survey Data, 2015

Training contributes to the personal development of the human resource. This, in the long run, contributes to the achievement of high quality and standards and continuous improvements in a school. Training ensures acquisition of skills and knowledge to be passed to learners.

STAFFING ON ECDE

On teachers Staffing, Analysis and interpretations revealed that twenty three (41.8) strongly Agreed (SA) that there were adequate teachers in ECDE, Twenty (36.4%) Agreed (A). This is shown in table 2.

Table 2. Whether there were adequate teachers in ECDE

Level response	Frequency	Percentage
Strong agreed (SA)	23	41.8
Agree (A)	20	36.4
UNDECIDED (U)	3	5.5
Disagree (D)	8	14.5
Strongly disagree (SD)	1	1.8
Total	55	100

Source: Survey Data, 2015

Knowledge of ECDE programs will ensure that teachers will be able to implement programs as desired and all parts of the curriculum will be attended to the satisfaction of all the stakeholders and the learners. The objectives of the curriculum will also be achieved accordingly.

CONCLUSION

Based on the results of the study, teachers have received sufficient training on ECD programs. Other than that, teachers are also encouraged to attend ECD training sessions so as to gain insights on the ECD curriculum. The school has also made a step towards enhancing the competency of the teachers. Specifically, the school has initiated an ECD skills training program meant for teachers so as to boost quality service delivery thereby fostering the implementation of ECD. Lack of funds for ECD training was found to impede implementation of ECD.

Moreover, it was evident from the study that the school hires highly qualified teachers. The schools intend to benefit from the wide array of skills brought on board by the highly qualified teachers. Besides, ECD teachers are evaluated in order to identify and resolve issues in ECD. Teachers are also encouraged to submit any queries to the school management.

It can be concluded that there are enough Trained Teachers in ECDE. Good teacher pupil ratio was realized in schools. Teachers are able to dispense the curriculum effectively as they are enough when it comes to allocation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

From the study findings, it was conceived that training and staffing are of the essence in ECD implementation. Thus, it is utmost necessary for schools to train their teachers so as to provide them with the necessary knowledge, skills, and understanding to successfully implement ECD programs. There is also a need for schools to initiate a training program in order to enhance teacher competency. It is also clear that lack of funds has impeded ECD implementation. Therefore, channeling sufficient funds would go a long way in enhancing ECD implementation.

The study also finds strong support for the argument that staffing has a positive influence on the implementation of early childhood education in ECD centers. ECD centers need to hire highly qualified teachers since they are best able to meet preschool program goals. With their knowledge, the developmentally appropriate curriculum is more likely to be chosen and used. Additionally, the school needs to evaluate teachers and encourage them to submit any queries to the school management.

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BIO DATA

ELSEBA JEPKOECH TOO has just graduated from the University of Eldoret in Education Management and Administration. She has been a teacher for twenty one years and has taught in Amani College of early childhood education, university of Eldoret part-time lecturer from the year 2012 to date. She hopes to pursue her Ph.D. in the same field.